

UNIVERSITY OF
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**Assessing the impact of mowing regimes on University
of Leicester greenspaces and their role in ecosystem
services (ES) provision**

Experimental Field Research Project

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Abstract

Mowing is a set pattern or frequency implemented in managing vegetation growth, prevent spread of invasive insects, and restore habitats to enhance pre-existing biodiversity. Periodic mowing holds an integral role in myriad of ecological interactions such as nutrient cycling, carbon sequestration, an increase in pollinator visit frequencies, and promoting ecological succession. However, recent studies indicate varying implications of mowing regimes towards ecosystem services(ES). Any direct or indirect benefits that humans derive from nature for their wellbeing are ecosystem services(ES). To investigate the diverse implications of mowing on tangible and intangible ES, 8 greenspaces across the University of Leicester campus were identified as wild, amenity and recreational grasslands based on the mowing regimes. Each site were surveyed using the standard Flower Insect Timed(FIT) count method to gain pollinator and plant insights and 'loss via ignition' methodology for soil. The results show a particular mowing regime applied on wildgrasslands support high pollinator abundance, plant species richness and diversity followed by amenity with moderate and recreational the least. Furthermore, the soil survey findings show mowing to not exhibit any statistically significant differences in organic matter content present in the soil. Although, amenity and recreational grasslands exhibited higher organic matter content followed by wildgrassland with the least, further in-depth soil-biochemistry research is required. The multivariate analyses show the presence of high variation in pollinator community composition across wildgrasslands, followed by moderate variation in amenity and least in recreational grassland. In addition, the plant community composition spanned across sites indicate wildgrasslands to exhibit significantly the highest variation in plants compared to amenity and recreational grasslands, which indicated moderate to least signifying the role of intricate ecological interactions and the impact of mowing on ecosystem services.

Introduction

Mowing of grasslands in urban spaces has driven widespread declines in biodiversity and ecosystem services (Proske et al., 2022). Numerous studies suggest mowing as one critical factor in influencing ecosystems amidst current high pace urbanization (Li et al., 2022). These semi-natural grasslands host nearly 50% of British and European species of butterflies and close to 80 species of plants per square meter signifying the importance of grasslands for supporting the chain of ecosystems (Bezzano 2018). However, as per recent studies-controlled mowing also promotes biological diversity and composition of species by

artificially reducing competition from tall growing or high nutrient demanding species (Hansson and Fogelfors 2000) (Huhta et al. 2001).

(Kremen, 2005) defines ecosystem services (ES) as to any resources and benefits that humans derive directly or indirectly from healthy ecosystems for functioning and sustenance of societies and categorizes these to be (i) provisioning services (ii) regulating services (iii) supporting services and (iv) cultural services. Despite increasing concern over the impact of mowing regimes on ES provided by semi grasslands, there is absence of quantification in anticipated effects of changing management regimes on varying variables. Multiple studies show the comparison between artificially intervened grasslands and naturally grown grasslands or mown versus unmown grasslands (Callaham et al., 2003). However, these studies lack to quantify the impact of varying management regimes applied on these grasslands (Blüthgen et al., 2012). One study also suggests as ES being inversely related to mowing frequencies in smaller grasslands as when disruptions in natural habitats are frequent, the abundance of invertebrates Hemiptera in particular decreased (Proske et al., 2022). In the hindsight, mowing frequencies are often correlated with the myriad of impacts it exerts on ES such as resource allocation on above-below ground life forms. For instance, it influences the soil biological activity, microbial biomass, pollination services and other major nutrient cycling efforts (Proske et al., 2022). Therefore, the major regulating ES are often the result of interwoven indirect ecological interactions and trade-offs between various dependent and independent components (Silwal et al., 2023). One urban wildlife experiment on mowing on rights-of-way (ROW) has showed how halting fertilizers and mowing for a year increased the number of monarch butterflies (*Danaus plexippus*) due to presence of milk weeds (*Asclepias syriaca*) signifying the intricate relationship between management regime and its effect on habitat as mowing altered the habitat structure and reduced predators meaning mowing created more of an open habitat structure best suited for monarch butterflies and also indirectly reduced other competitors leading to higher survivability (Leston and Koper, 2019). Likewise, study done by (Ding et al., 2021) shows how addition of Nitrogen (N) enrichment on grassland's forage yield increased growth in rhizomatic species of plants along with concentrations of crude protein and fat whereas mowing in contrast weakened the positive forage yield capacity in grasslands by drastic reduction in the biomass and nutrient depletion. This demonstrated the impact of mowing on ES where forage yield can be categorized as provisioning services under ES. However, another study done on a temperate grassland under N enrichment condition showed how mowing enhanced the species richness and plant diversity level but also exacerbated the negative impacts of N addition on ecosystem stability, it showed synchronised fluctuations in abundance of plant populations in response to mowing and other environmental changes whilst also increasing the variability of primary productivity meaning production of biomass in mown areas fluctuated more than in unmown areas (Zhang et al., 2017).

The urban greenspaces are integral part of sustainable cities which enables wide range of ecosystem services to human beings (Silwal et al., 2023). The greenspaces within the University campus also exhibits multiple such ecologically rich and suitable study areas, that potentially contribute to myriad of functions and vitality of the landscape. The strategic study sites within the Leicester city potentially enables the provision of ES (ref. Fig.1). These greenspaces span an array of grasslands from expansive wild grasslands to finely manicured

amenity and recreational grasslands, each comprising of its own salient ecological significance (ref.Fig.1).

The aim of this study is to scientifically assess the ecosystem services(ES) provided by a multitude of greenspaces spanning the University of Leicester campus, with a particular focus on comprehending the impact of three mowing regimes applied onto three different grassland types, geographically located in different campus location based in Leicester. The research is divided into three experimental sub-aspects each comprising of their own ecological significance as an indicator to narrow down the broad research question of assessing ecosystem services. The first investigation is aimed to quantify the abundance level of pollinators present across all the study areas by understanding the impact of mowing regimes applied onto them. The second investigation is to observe impact of mowing regimes on grasslands and analyse plant diversity and species richness level and lastly the third study is to assess the carbon sequestration capacity in the soil present across all study sites particularly the organic matter content. The combination of outcomes from these three domains will help us build a pragmatic discussion in understanding the influence of management practices on grasslands and any other confounding factors that are associated with ES.

From the outcome of the study, I aim to ultimately understand if mowing frequencies has any impact on grasslands and on regulating ecosystem services we receive as beneficiaries from the environment. I also aim to understand if alteration in mowing practice holds any positive implication in ES we receive and further explore future prospects and applications of any other alternative management approaches that can be implemented from an ecological standpoint to improve existing ecological services and enhance our understanding with evidence-based decision-making towards sustainable urban ES.

Materials and Methods

2.1 Study site description

The survey period spanned from 21st July until 2nd September 2023, where daily site observations were meticulously carried out at eight different grasslands spread across the University of Leicester Campus, encompassing three distinct management regimes. The green survey sites were strategically located in close proximity to the main campus with three recreational grassland sites being located around the Oadby campus premises. Out of eight, a total of three sites were classified as wild grassland, two as amenity and three as recreational grasslands. All eight grasslands were subject to three different management regimes applied onto them. Wild grassland underwent annual or biannual mowing, amenity grasslands were mowed every two weeks in season whereas recreational grasslands were mowed and fertilised every 3 weeks. The mowing operations were carried out by the

University grounds and gardening team. Each replicate sites were assigned a two-letter appendix to mark grasslands(refFig.1).

Wild grasslands: (Main Campus – FJB Forest Garden & Entrance 3, Stoughton Road Pitches)

Amenity (non-fertilised) grasslands: (Main Campus – FJB lawn, Michael Atiyah, FJB Quads)

Recreational (fertilised) grasslands: (Oadby – Stoughton Road Pitches, Roger Bettles Running Track)

Figure1: Satellite mapped grasslands across University of Leicester campus (Adapted from Google Maps, 2023)
 The figure shows the compilation of 8 survey sites where Site AA, AB and AC are under Wildgrasslands followed by Site AD, AE under Amenity(non-fertilised) grasslands and Site AG and AI under Recreational grasslands each allocated to particular mowing regimes.

2.2 What3words mapping

What3words is a geocoding mobile application system used for assigning a unique 3-word code address to every 3x3 meter square on the earth's surface(Arthur, 2023). In the context of conducting surveys, the application was used to map out each grassland and their

replicate sites with 3x3 meter square grids and each grid were assigned with a particular corresponding number within the site's boundary. The grids were made to achieve high level precision in poorly framed or in complex topographical regions to place quadrats. The app was used in placing quadrats with no human bias to randomise the data collection.

2.3 Flower-Insect Timed (FIT) count

Flower Insect Timed count or FIT counts can be understood as a surveying method used to observe and quantify the total number of insects that visit a particular flower or a square patch of about 50x50 cm within a standard timeframe of 10 minutes (Soares et al., 2023). This method was essentially used to obtain insights about pollinator visits, interactions and their abundance. The 50x50 cm quadrats were placed on grids from the What3words application every 10 minutes in random spots within the sites (Haas et al., 2005). A total of 128 surveys from 8 sites were taken where 16 surveys from each allocated replicate sites were surveyed when temperature ranges were above 13°C.

2.4 Vegetation Quadrat Sampling and Identification

A total of 80 quadrat samples were taken from 8 replicate sites to identify various species of plants at the group level. This was done by placing the 50x50 cm quadrat onto randomized grid generated by the random number generator and identified diverse group of plants found within that quadrat by using Collins Flower-Guide by (David, 2009) and PlantNet mobile application (Hart et al., 2023) which worked in conjunction to identify plants when subject to live photograph taken and compared from their internal web repository. Thereby, a total of 51 different species of plants were identified across all 8 grasslands.

Species richness data were calculated per each quadrat sample to assess the number of various plants species found in that defined area distributed across all 8 study sites. A presence- absence matrix method was adopted to assess richness and diversity per site grouped according to their respective management regimes. To assess the diversity of plants, Simpson diversity index (SDI) was implemented where D denotes Diversity Index, N = total number of species, and n denotes = presence or absence of particular (n^{th}) species used the formula $D = 1 - (\sum n(n-1)) / (N(N-1))$.

2.5 Soil organic matter content sampling

A total of 32 soil samples were collected using the Edelman auger from 12th–16th November 2023, to determine the organic matter content found in the soil. The Edelman auger was used to dig layers of disturbed heavily rooted soil below 5m from the surface onto 8 different study sites. The samples were taken to the geography lab to determine organic matter content by assessing via loss on ignition. The soil samples were initially oven dried in the lab for 14 hours prior to being placed into the furnace. An empty mass of crucible was weighed on an analytical balance as M_c = (mass of container) and the dried soil samples weighed between approx. 5-20g were put into the crucibles as M_{105} = (mass of sample after oven drying plus container). The furnace was calibrated at 550°C temperature to burn off

any excess moisture or organic matter in the soil for 4 hours. The samples were put inside the desiccator for a period of 10 minutes to cool down the crucibles and re-weighed on an analytical balance as M_{550} = (mass of sample after ignition at 550°C plus container). The organic matter content of each soil sample from study sites were calculated and derived using the formula: %Organic Matter content= $(M_{105}-M_{550}) / (M_{105}-M_c) \times 100$ (Towler, 2023).

2.6 Statistical Data Analyses

All analyses were undertaken in R version 4.3.1 using an exploratory non-parametric analysis model. The exploratory data analysis (EDA) was carried out first to understand the characteristics distribution of the dataset across all three grasslands (Wild, Amenity and Recreational grasslands) comprising of 8 sites. To visually understand the distribution and normality of the dataset, QQ-plots were generated. The QQ-plot in conjunction to Shapiro Wilk Normality test were used to infer the normality between mowing regimes across study sites. Consequently, when the normality of the dataset was evaluated, a non-parametric statistical model was adopted given the non-normal distribution of the dataset.

For assessing the significance difference level between variables such as (Pollinator Abundance, Plant Species Richness and Organic Matter content found in soil) versus management regimes applied onto them, the analyses were carried out in a hierarchical order. To assess the impact of regimes, the grasslands were first assessed in response to the regimes followed by each replicate sites grouped by their corresponding grasslands. The comparative responses or significant difference in variables (type of grassland and grouped sites) based on management regimes were obtained through Kruskal Wallis test and variables grouped by (only replicate sites) were obtained via post-hoc Dunn test to spot any inter group significant differences from one another.

Similarly, an ANOSIM (Analysis of Similarities) was performed to spot variation between community composition of plant and pollinator species, whilst also to spot similarities between sites subject to distinct mowing regimes. In addition, a Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) was performed to visualise the distribution of community matrices via DCA plots.

Results

3.1 Statistical differences under varying mowing regimes

3.1.1 Pollinator abundance Analysis

To assess whether mowing regimes impact the abundance levels of pollinators, a statistical normality test was performed to check the pattern and distribution of the dataset. Here, Shapiro Wilk-Normality test was employed, and the p-value was observed to be $4.313e^{-05}$

which is smaller than the commonly set significance level ($p < 0.05$), the dataset appeared to be not normal. Given the non-parametric nature, a Kruskal-Wallis test was initially performed to observe the significance difference between all three management regimes corresponding to respective 3 grasslands (wild, amenity and recreational) versus the pollinator abundance level. The obtained Kruskal-Wallis chi-square test when showed significant difference ($\chi^2 = 57.28$, $df = 2$, $p = 3.646e^{-13}$) between various regimes, a post-hoc Dunn test was further performed to investigate the pair-wise comparison between each regime to understand the differences. All acquired post-hoc p-values were subject to Bonferroni correction to adjust for multiple comparisons. The analysis revealed no significant differences in abundance level of pollinators between grasslands which were “cut every 3 weeks and fertilised” vs “cut every 2 weeks in season” ($Z = 1.087$, $p = 0.45154$) which is greater $p \geq 0.05$. Nonetheless the comparisons between “cut every 3 weeks & fertilised” vs “Mowed once or twice a year” and “cut every 2 weeks in season” vs “mowed once or twice a year” revealed a significant difference in pollinator abundance level as the p-values on both pair wise comparison ($Z = -5.339$, $p < .001$) and ($Z = -7.185$, $p < .001$) were smaller than ($p < 0.05$).

3.1.2 Plant species richness

To investigate potential variation in species richness level of plants, the same statistical approach was taken as pollinators where normality of plants were statistically tested and upon performing Shapiro Wilk-Normality test, the obtained p-value $4.467e^{-08}$ was observed to be not normal therefore leading to further analysis to Kruskal Wallis test since the p-value was less than the significance level of ($p < 0.05$), therefore rejecting null-hypothesis. The Kruskal-Wallis chi-square test performed between species richness level of plants across three mowing regimes and corresponding grasslands yielded a non-significant difference ($\chi^2 = 32.46$, $df = 2$, $p = 8.906e^{-08}$) where $p \geq 0.05$. Nonetheless, the specific differences on plants species richness were further analysed via post-hoc Dunn test where pair-wise comparison between grasslands “cut every 3 weeks & fertilised” vs cut every 2 weeks in season” obtained ($Z = 2.852201$, $p = 0.0065126$) which indicates significant difference as ($p < 0.05$). All acquired post-hoc test p-values were subject to Bonferroni correction to adjust for multiple comparisons and comparison between “cut every 3 weeks & fertilised” vs “mowed once or twice a year” also obtained ($Z = -2.234953$, $p = 0.00$) indicating high significant difference. Lastly, comparison between “cut every 2 weeks in season” vs “mowed once or twice a year” obtained ($Z = -5.687612$, $p = 0.0381$) where $p < 0.05$ indicating a significant difference.

3.1.3 Soil Organic Matter (SOM)

To assess the variation in organic matter content present in the soil, the same statistical protocol was implemented as other two elements (see methods). Upon performing Shapiro Wilk-normality test, obtained p-value was 0.0109 which is smaller $\alpha = 0.05$ level, therefore using the non-parametric approach, Kruskal-Wallis chi-square test acquired ($\chi^2 = 3.75$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.1531$). Further, a post-hoc Dunn test was performed to acquire pair-wise comparison of mowing regimes where grasslands “cut every 3 weeks & fertilised” vs “cut every 2 weeks in

season" obtained ($Z= 1.747$, $p= 0.12093$) indicating no significance due to $p \geq 0.05$. Likewise, "cut every 3 weeks & fertilised" vs "Mowed Once or Twice a year" obtained ($Z= 1.717$, $p=1.0$) . Lastly, comparison between "cut every 2 weeks in season" vs. "Mowed Once or Twice a year" regime($Z= -0.0326$, $p= 0.1287$) . Hence, the results of all three pair-wise comparisons obtained p-values greater than $\alpha = 0.05$ level indicating no significance difference in the organic matter content found in the soil across all 8 grasslands irrespective of any mowing regimes applied onto them. All acquired post-hoc test p-values were subject to Bonferroni correction to adjust for multiple comparisons.

3.2 Plant Diversity across sites

To assess the diversity of plants, Simpson diversity index (SDI) calculation was performed on obtained 51 species of plants where presence-absence metrics was taken into consideration. Initially, the calculation was performed fundamentally on three grasslands (wild, amenity and recreational). The wildgrassland=0.099717, amenity=0.94285 and recreational=0.69776 meaning wildgrassland indicated higher diversity and evenness, followed by amenity with moderate diversity and recreational with relatively low diversity. Likewise, a site specific calculation revealed rather different values where under wildgrasslands Site AA=0.9964, AB=0.9968, AC=0.9983 and under amenity grasslands, site AD=0.9993, AE=0.99989 and under recreational grasslands AG=0.9982, AH=0.9955 and AI=0.9975 . The site-specific diversity values closely correlate with the fundamental calculation based on grasslands.

3.3 Multivariate analysis

To investigate the interrelatedness of plants and pollinators in influencing the ES, an ANOSIM (Analysis of Similarities) statistical test was performed where initially community composition of 51 plant species were taken into consideration linked with management regimes applied onto those respective 8 study sites where mowing regimes were applied. The obtained R-statistic value=0.7121 indicated moderate to strong dissimilarity in plant communities present in grasslands where respective mowing regimes were applied. In addition, the acquired p-value=0.0125 which is ($p<0.05$) reaffirmed the dissimilarity between communities of plants across grasslands indicating the presence of statistical significance. Likewise, the same statistical approach performed on pollinator abundance data also showed similar result where R -statistic value=0.65 indicating moderate level of dissimilarity of pollinator communities across all study sites with $p=0.019$ also being ($p<0.05$) indicating the significant difference in the pollinator communities.

Figure 2: **Distribution of pollinator community composition post-mowing in different grasslands.** The DCA plot shows variation in pollinators. Panel (a) depicts overall variation observed in site corresponding grasslands indicated by coloured bubbles and characterised by an ellipse. Panel (b) shows distribution of common pollinators close to ellipse and scarce ones farther away in the plot indicating larger variation.

- Species
- Calycine Hawthorn
 - Noble Yarrow
 - Common Bent
 - Wavy Hair grass
 - Tufted Hair grass
 - Alpine Marsh Violet
 - European Black Berry
 - Smooth Cat's ear
 - Club Spikemoss
 - Gesylva
 - Self Heal
 - Rock cotoneaster
 - English Hawthorn
 - Dutch elm
 - Dwarf mallow
 - English Ivy
 - Spreading Bent
 - Cock's foot
 - Sweetbriar
 - Narrow leaf Plantain
 - Dogwood
 - Common White Heart leaf aster
 - Creeping thistle
 - Yorkshire fog
 - Germander speedwell
 - Lime
 - Creeping Buttercup
 - Hairy Tare
 - Golden ragwort
 - Plantain grass
 - Greater bird's foot-trefoil
 - Wood Bluegrass
 - Heath False brome
 - Mugwort
 - Spear thistle
 - Bristly oxtongue
 - Ground Ivy
 - Loose silky bent
 - Hoary Ragwort
 - European Dunegrass
 - Waterdock
 - Broad Leaved dock
 - Bushgrass
 - Blackwell switchgrass
 - Strawberry Clover
 - Poaecoe
 - White Clover
 - Black Medick
 - Autumn Hawkbit
 - English cinefoil
 - Bermudagrass

Figure 3: Distribution of plant community composition post-mowing in different grasslands. The DCA plot shows variation in plant species. Panel (a) depicts overall variation observed in site corresponding grasslands indicated by coloured bubbles and characterised by an ellipse. Panel (b) shows distribution of common or repeated plants close to specific ellipse and scarce diverse plants farther away in the plot indicating variation.

Note: There are total of all 51 species indicated in the plot, however multiple sites comprising of same ordnance and eigenvalues depicts overlapping and stacking of bubbles obscuring the view.

Discussion

4.1 Effects of mowing regimes on Pollinator abundance, plant species richness-diversity and carbon sequestration capacity in soil

The results obtained from statistical analyses indicate mowing to not exhibit any effect in the number of pollinating insects when grasslands are mowed every 2 or 3 weeks in season but discernible impact is evident when mowed frequently or mowed once or twice a year(ref.Fig.4b).

Figure 4: **Effects of three distinct mowing regimes on pollinator abundance level.** The boxplot shows the distribution of observed data where: panel (a) depicts the abundance level by regimes and panel(b) shows the abundance level by replicate sites corresponding to respective grasslands.

This discrepancy in pollinator abundance is also hypothesised in previous studies where a five-year field study observed increase in the number of wild bees, hoverflies when subject to delayed or infrequent mowing and resulted in higher abundance of pollinators (Wu et al., 2023). Most recent studies by (Lerman et al., 2018) also hypothesize the reduction in abundance level of pollinators due to infrequent mowing as certain species of pollinator such as squash bees (*Peponapis pruinosa*) were observed to be dependent on specific plant species for habitat, pollen and nectar as opposed to those such as European honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) which were dependent on other wide range of readily available plant species for foraging and habitat. This correlation can also be re-affirmed from the varying variation observed across all 8 sites in plant community composition where pollinator dependency was prevalent (ref.Fig.2b & 3b).

On the other hand, the plant species richness analyses indicate relatively significant difference in their richness level when subject to all three distinct mowing regimes. Based on the findings, Wildgrassland displays to have highest level of plant richness as shown in (Fig.5a) followed by moderate richness in amenity and less in recreational grasslands. This could likely be due to edge and spillover effects. A study conducted on 51 similar sites previously suggests how grasslands adjacent to one another sharing boundaries form an edge habitat zone and receive an intermediate level of resources and disturbance as opposed to other and support species irrespective of any mowing frequencies(Wang et al., 2022). This edge habitat in turn supports species of disturbed plants from both the sites via vegetative propagation where plants develop and spread vegetative propagules resulting in species richness variation(Wang et al., 2022). This study clearly aligns well with the findings as 7 out of 8 replicate sites shared common boundaries(ref.Fig.1).

In addition, a study done on semi-natural grasslands also shows how moderate mowing frequency promote high species richness by halting the dominance of competitive species such as Meadow Foxtail (*Alopecurus pratensis*), White Clover (*Trifolium repens*) and Tufted hair grass (*Deschampsia cespitosa*) which in turn increases the habitat heterogeneity by forming suitable patch spaces and microhabitats for niches and ruderal and stress tolerant species to co-exist(Gerrard, 2008). Interestingly, the same dominance phenomenon could likely have occurred across the study sites as it can be observed in wildgrasslands with same species of plants as (Gerrard, 2008) being present across grasslands shown in (ref.Fig.3b), however it demands further investigation.

Figure 5: Effects of three distinct mowing regimes on plant species richness level. The boxplot shows the distribution of observed data where: panel (a) depicts the species richness level by regimes and panel (b) shows the richness level by replicate sites corresponding to respective grasslands.

In contrast, amenity and recreational grasslands exhibit less richness level likely due to uniform mowing frequency favouring only competitive species such as Bermudagrass (*Cynodon dactylon*) or plants under Poaceae family (as shown in DCA plot Fig.3b). which are potentially adapted to specific regime and Nitrogen as fertilizer. A study by (Peter et al., 2011) also shows how plants under Poaceae family are predominantly resilient and adapted to frequent grazing as they possess rhizomatous and stoloniferous growth pattern which helps them in recovering from post-mowing event and outcompete other species resulting in less species richness in that particular area.

Another study also suggests how plant species under Poaceae family produce an allelopathic compound called dhurrin that inhibits the growth and suppresses the germination of neighbouring plant species(Willis et al., 1999). Hence, resulting in less species richness in that area. These studies do provide compelling potential assumptions of mowing’s impact however, an in-depth further investigation on such particular plants is required for conclusive understanding(Kilmes and Ova, 2007).

Figure 6: SDI plant diversity observed across distinct grasslands and replicate sites. The bar plot shows the obtained Simpson diversity result of plants found across campus greenspaces where RED bar shows the general diversity categorised by grasslands and BLUE shows diversity obtained from replicate sites.

Similarly, the acquired Simpson Diversity Index(SDI) findings suggest similar influence of reduced mowing on grasslands in facilitating diversity. One study by (Huston 2014) suggests how exposed patches in the site is colonized and adapted by pioneer plant and fast growing species of shrubs such as Blackberry(*Rubus subg*) which leads to creation of diverse niche where several plants compete for nutrients and sunlight resulting in creation of multi layered diverse ecosystems for new species to co-exist and thrive. In contrast, past research also

mentions the role of stress-gradient hypothesis(SGH) theory in shaping the diversity of plants where for instance, plants present in grasslands closer to the disturbance proximity leads to act as a Nurse plant where tufts of *Festuca (Festuca ovina)* plant provides a microhabitat to smaller or more susceptible species of plants as a shield from any desiccation or mowing pressure, ultimately creating favourable conditions in survival and enhancement of species diversity(Connell and Slatyer , 1977).

Figure 7: Effects of three distinct mowing regimes on organic matter content found in the soil. The boxplot shows the distribution of observed data where: panel (a) organic matter content by regimes and panel(b) shows the organic matter content by replicate sites corresponding to respective grasslands.

Likewise, based on the findings the soil organic matter content analyses display no significant difference irrespective of any mowing regimes applied onto the grasslands.

However, mowing every 2 to 3 weeks and fertilising grasslands revealed higher organic matter content compared to wildgrassland which were mowed in biannual basis. Surprisingly, this result contradicts when compared with conventional ramification of mowing where frequent mowing usually results in more accumulation of litter and more accumulation of litter results to more organic matter reserve underneath the soil(Yang et al., 2022). This could be due to several biotic and abiotic factors, however a study done for 30-year in chronosequence shows how microbial necromass in managed grasslands contribute significantly to increased soil organic matter (SOM), as bacteria-derived carbon residue significantly contribute to soil organic carbon(SOC) compared to fungal and plant litter residues(Yang et al., 2022). The change in this shift was due to quick bacterial growth rate and increased accumulation of bacterial biomass residues, ultimately, leading to high soil organic matter (Yang et al., 2022). This indicates the potential presence of rich microbial life in amenity and recreational grasslands, however further research is required to gain firm understanding. Previous studies by(Wu et al., 2022)and (Ding et al., 2021) also revealed implication of mowing which emphasizes the role of Nitrogen deposition and accumulation of mowed grass clippings that leads to quick compensatory growth in roots and turnover when climate is warm resulting in increment of root biomass. Therefore, it shows how the combined effect of mowing, Nitrogen fertilisation and weather as confounding factor influence SOM significantly(Gong et al., 2019).

4.2 Interconnected nature of pollinator, plants and soil condition in supporting ES

The findings also suggest the likelihood of changes in one aspect such as plant community potentially influence the other such as pollinating insects and vice versa. This mutual interaction is evident in wildgrasslands(ref.Fig.3b & 4b), where richness and diverse plant communities potentially provided conducive ecosystem for pollinating insects to thrive as opposed to amenity and recreational grasslands with less variation in plant supporting significantly less number of pollinators. A study by (Francini et al., 2022) also shows how pollinator play a crucial role as dispersal agents in regulating and facilitating genetic variation in plants to diversify the communities whilst also receiving nectar and habitat in return. This trade-off therefore reaffirms the complex dependency of plant and pollinators in supporting ES where both element reciprocates by tolerating biotic and abiotic stressors and provide ES via controlling pests, flood, storm , fungal infestations, initiating phytoremediation during pollution and production of foods for humans(Francini et al., 2022).

Likewise, organic matter content obtained across grasslands also exhibit the correlation with plant communities as composition of Poaceae family grass present in recreational sites possessed higher organic matter content compared to other sites which had varied plant composition as shown on (Fig.3b & 7b).This could potentially be due to many factors but one study done on (*Gentiana aristata*) shows how the moisture of soil attributes to variation in phenotypical traits of plants and thus influence the pollinator visiting frequency(Dai et al., 2022). This reciprocal interaction therefore shows the interdependency of soil, plants and pollinator on one another. Another investigation demonstrated similar finding where stimulation of microbial activity led to decomposing leftover plant residues

ultimately being converted to organic matter due to humification and increment in soil organic matter(Ayers , 2023).

Based on findings, the stimulation in amenity and recreational grasslands could have potentially initiated by anthropogenic factor such as constant trampling from athletes who engaged in sports activities resulting in soil compaction and sudden shift in soil chemistry, ultimately influencing the outcome of the research. Another study by (Ma et al., 2021) also reveals how Nitrogen fertiliser initiate feedback-loop between plants and soil where the accumulation of mowed grass facilitates nutrients below ground enriching the soil through root turnover rate and humification. This trade-off between soil and plant indeed shows the intricate ecological dynamics responsible in supporting ES which captures excess carbon from the atmosphere into the soil as SOM functions like the carbon sink and provide benefit by reducing risks of erosion(Ma et al., 2021). In contrast, 5 out of 8 grasslands under amenity and wildgrassland exhibited significantly low organic matter likely due to the presence of certain plant and pollinator community composition(Fig 2b & 3b). Past studies conducted by (Jilkova et al., 2023) and (Harling et al., 2022) shows how dominance of grass species such as Bermudagrass or C4 grasses and lack of leguminous plants such as Perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perence*) influence the ability of soil to fix atmospheric nitrogen using rhizobium bacteria and limits plant growth whilst also leaving soil Nitrogen deficit causing less soil organic matter. This can therefore also be potentially the reason why wildgrasslands possessed less organic matter due to presence of bermudagrass and lack of leguminous plant composition as shown (ref.Fig.3b).

Previous studies have shown the role of woody and forb species of plant such as Honey mesquite (*Prosopis glandulosa*) that facilitates in soil penetration using taproots below the top soil horizons whereas litters produced from woody plants generate high lignin content that leads to slow decomposition compared to labile litter producing plants(Han et al., 2022). This variation in plant community composition could be one primary factor in observing significantly less soil organic matter content in all 3 replicate sites of wildgrassland and 2 sites of amenity. This shows the symbiotic mutual dependency of plants and soil in providing regulating, provisioning and supporting ecosystem services all together as organic matter allows soil to gain a structure and porosity which helps in retaining and regulating the water for mitigating drought, surface water runoff and nectar production for pollinators all in a cascading manner(Zhou et al., 2017).

4.3 Determining Ecosystem Services (ES) provided by grasslands

The pollinator, plant and soil composition metrics can be correlated as proxies or indicators in assessing the ES where observed high pollinator abundance level across grasslands can be associated with presence of diverse plant species and increased pollination services due to abundant source of nectar, seed and habitats, ultimately leading to increment in reproductive succession and providing provisioning services such as food production, carbon capture etc(Solen et al., 2017). Likewise, one study by (Czúcz et al., 2020) also shows high soil organic matter content serve as a sponge to retain water and nutrients for plants in

contributing to plant diversity and enhance carbon sequestration process providing regulating and supporting services.

This complex reciprocal ecological interaction indeed support our observation from the findings as Wildgrasslands possess comparatively high amount of pollinator abundance and plant species diversity, meaning the sites potentially provide regulating and supporting services whereas based on statistical findings, amenity grasslands possess the highest amount of organic matter content followed by recreational and wildgrasslands. This can be attributed to amenity grasslands providing significant regulating and cultural services that involves high soil carbon to mitigate risks of urban flood, storm water runoff, water purification and also provide an aesthetic appealing space for human wellbeing to connect with nature. Similarly, the recreational grasslands also provide ES moderately equivalent to amenity through regulating services and cultural services where humans are given designated turf greenspace to practice sports activities.

4.4 Limitations

The experimental field study encountered 5 major limitations. One primary constraint among many was sudden change in weather conditions as the standard FIT count method required relatively sunny and dry weather to survey pollinators only between 10am to 3pm. The sudden unpredicted shift in weather rather disrupted surveys resulting insects in hiding and entering a state of dormancy until dry and favourable again. A four-year study on butterfly behaviour shows similar effect as butterflies preferred flying more and resting less in warmer sites compared to wet or windy(Kral O'Brien, 2021). Likewise, the limited duration of study to complete surveys also posed a setback in surveying insects as the standard methodology required to completing surveys before the onset of winter i.e. September resulting in rather a smaller number of sample collection, reduced reliability and statistical significance. One study demonstrates how less sample size collection leads to inflated gaps in ordination metrics and type II errors during analysis(Hallman and Robinson 2020). Similarly, the edge effect is also one potential limitation as 7 out of 8 survey sites shared common boundary with not much gap in between, this could have likely led to unwanted dispersal and sharing of seeds , resources across multiple sites influencing the robustness of the samples(Kitti et al., 2021).This is evident from past researches where smaller fragmented grassland receive more seed dispersal and predation compared to bigger grasslands due to edge to interior ratio(Kitti et al., 2021). Likewise, the Beaufort scale assessment input could also be one limitation as judging windspeed, sunlight intensity and tree coverage involved intrinsic human bias inherently involving an element of uncertainty affecting the placements of quadrats. A study by (Hoodless et al., 2006) on populations of breeding Snipe (*Gallinago gallinago*) shows how observer bias and overestimation resulted in skewed statistical analyses. Varying topography of grasslands could also be another limitation as sites located in different topography might have acquired certain microclimatic exposure and influenced sites in receiving uneven amount of sunlight or resources leading to potential biases in sampling interpretations. A study conducted on semi-arid forest grassland strongly shows how differences in elevation and exposure of sunlight alters the structure, niches and variation in plant species(Plaisted et al., 2023).

4.5 Future strategies and integrated holistic approach to optimize ES across the campus

Based on the findings, the studied greenspaces across the University of Leicester campus exhibit substantial amount of evidence supporting the presence of healthy ecosystem services. However, it also lacks strategic management approach in optimising the ES. This can be achieved by introducing native species of plants in wildgrasslands such as English lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*), Betony(*Stachys officinalis*), herb plant like fennel(*Foeniculum vulgare*) and plants with strong scents such as sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) as these plants are well known for retaining a wide range of pollinators including butterflies, beetles and moths which comparatively seemed to be less abundant across the sites(Fig.2b). These plants particularly comprise of sturdy structure, strong scent and shallow corollas that can support overlooked and endangered pollinators in pollination ultimately enhancing the existing pollination diversity and indirectly providing regulatory ES. A study done by (Slachta et al., 2022) reveals how Mason bees(*Osmia bicornis*) are active and function early season in urban grasslands even before bumble bees to pollinate plants with no sting threat indirectly providing cultural ecosystem services to humans along with efficient pollination as regulatory services. Likewise, introducing plants with varied bloom times can also promote pollinators in receiving a continuous supply of nectar and pollen throughout the year irrespective of any weather conditions. For example, one recent study shows how planting Magnolias (*Magnolia virginiana*) in spring, lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) in summer and Pansies (*Viola tricolor*) in winter considerably provide consistent amount of nectar, pollen and ultimately regulatory ES(Ulrich et al., 2021). Similarly, the implementation of scallop mowing pattern in amenity grasslands can also enhance the aesthetic appeal whilst contributing to ES. A study done on an urban greenspace mimicking grazing pattern shows how creating attractive patterns, shapes and contours leaving longer grass patches untouched, support existing pollinator and plant diversity whilst also providing aesthetic and cultural ES(Duarte et al., 2018). In addition, the use of geospatial data and analytical tool such as InVEST(Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Trade-offs) can be installed to map, simulate and quantify the synergies between multiple elements responsible for ecosystem services. A study conducted by (Li et al., 2023) shows how utilization of this tool can be useful in tracing sudden shifts in soil organic carbon content, floral diversity and diversity of pollinators to assess the health of ecosystems and rolling out necessary mitigatory strategies and restore the equilibrium of ES before the onset of any natural calamities such as storm or heatwaves.

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